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ON THE CHECKLIST OF UKRAINIAN DIPTERA TEPHRITOIDEA: TEPHRITIDAE

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Korneyev, V. A. On the checklist of Ukrainian Diptera Tephritoidea: Tephritidae. — An annotated list includes 141 species recorded from Ukraine, with 75 species from Kyiv oblast (region), 63 from Luhansk oblast, 57 from Ternopil oblast, 54 from Cherkasy oblast and 48 from Crimea. At the same time, 0 species were recorded from Vohlyn and Dnipropetrovsk oblasts, and only 1–5 species from Rivne, Zhytomyr, Sumy, Lviv, Khmelnytsky, Vinnytsia, Poltava, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kirovohrad, Donetsk and Zaporizhzhya oblasts, showing that Ukrainian fruit flies are still very unevenly sampled and that more focused collecting trips are needed. At least 21 species are expected to be found, mainly in the Carpathians and the steppes of southern Ukraine.

Key words: Ukraine, true fruit flies, checklist.

Корнєв, В. О. До чек-листу українських видів двокрилих підродини Tephritoidea: Tephritidae. — До анотованого списку включено 141 вид з України, з них 75 видів з Київської області, 63 — з Луганської, 57 — з Тернопільської, 54 — з Черкаської та 48 — з Криму. У той же час, 0 видів було зареєстровано з Волинської та Дніпропетровської областей, і лише 1–5 видів з Рівненської, Житомирської, Сумської, Львівської, Хмельницької, Вінницької, Полтавської, Івано-Франківської, Кіровоградської, Донецької та Запорізької областей, що свідчить про те, що українські плодові мухи все ще дуже нерівномірно представлені у колекційних матеріалах, і що необхідні більш цілеспрямовані експедиційні виїзди для колектування. Очікується, що буде знайдено щонайменше двадцять один вид, переважно в Карпатах і степах на півдні України.

Ключові слова: Україна, мухи-осетниці, список видів.

Introduction

The Tephritidae, or true fruit flies, with ca. 5000 species (Norrbom, pers. comm.), is the largest family in the superfamily Tephritidae (Pape et al., 2011); except for flies of a few Old World tribes with saprophagous larvae, most tephritids are phytophagous (Korneyev, 1999).

Studies of the tephritid flies in Ukraine began with the description of *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld, 1867 (Tephritidae) and lists of flies collected in Podolien (now Ternopil Region of Ukraine) (Wierzejski, 1867; Nowicki, 1899), with the collection being deposited mainly in the State Museum of Natural History, Lviv, and partly in the Natural History Museum, Vienna. Later, Jaroszewski (1877 a, b, 1878, 1880, 1882, 1886) published a series of Diptera lists based on his collection specimens, mostly identified by I.A. Portschinsky or himself, and now deposited in the Zoological Institute, St. Petersburg (ZISP) and the Natural History Museum, Kharkiv University. A few species of Tephritoidea collected in the Middle Dnipro

area in 1933–1936 were identified by A.A. Stackelberg and then published by O.P. Kryshstal (1949). In the last 40 years a large amount of material has been collected and partly published by V. A. Korneyev, E. P. Kameneva and S. V. Korneyev in different parts of Ukraine (see checklist below). Photographs of the tephritid collection deposited at the Vernadsky University of Simferopol (VUS), taken by G. Popov in 2012, were used to confirm the presence of species on the Crimean peninsula; as the exact text of the labels cannot be read, I refer to “VUS” where necessary.

No comprehensive catalogues of Palaearctic species have been published since Foote (1984) and Norrbom et al. (1999). The only lists or databases of European species are those of Merz & Korneyev (2004, 2013). Currently, the number of Tephritidae species is close to the estimated number. We expect up to 21 additional species of the Tephritidae in steppes and the Carpathian mountains.

The territory of Ukraine is unevenly covered by collecting, and many field and museum specimens are to be added to the Ukrainian National Biodiversity Information

Network (UkrBIN, 2024a). This would certainly extend the known distribution of most species in the country, which are now restricted to a few popular localities around large cities. The present paper provides a list of species based on the published data with some previously unpublished additions. The genera and species are listed in alphabetical order. In Distribution, the provinces (regions, oblasts) are listed from west to east and from north to south. As a result, 141 species of Tephritidae are listed.

Synonymy of species names is not given unless the species was mentioned as a synonym in the cited literature; for a complete list of synonyms see Norrbom et al. (1999).

New records for regions are indicated by asterisks.

If not stated otherwise, the data on the associations with host plants are based on the papers listed in **References** and **Remarks**.

Results

By now, 141 species have been recorded from Ukraine, with 72 species from Kyiv oblast (region), 62 from Luhansk oblast, 57 from Ternopil oblast, 54 from Cherkasy oblast and 48 from Crimea. At the same time, 0 species were recorded from Vohlyn and Dnipropetrovsk oblasts, and only 1–5 species from Rivne, Zhytomyr, Sumy, Lviv, Khmelnytsky, Vinnytsia, Poltava, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kirovohrad, Donetsk and Zaporizhzhia oblasts, showing that Ukrainian fruit flies are still very unevenly sampled and that more focused collecting trips are needed. At least twenty-one species are expected to be found, mainly in the Carpathians and the steppes of southern Ukraine.

Checklist

1. *Acanthophilus helianthi* (Rossi, 1794)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Mykolaiv; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 b) (as *Tephritis eluta*); V. Korneyev (1985b); Korneyev & Konovalov (2010); Korneyev et al. (2016); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Associated with most species of *Centaurea* occurring in Ukraine (as well as *Carthamus* and *Psephellus*) and apparently widespread in all parts of Ukraine.

2. *Acidia cognata* (Wiedemann, 1817)

Distribution in Ukraine: Zhytomyr*; Kyiv; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Crimea*.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); S. Korneyev (2011).

Remarks. In shady, humid places, in association with *Tussilago* and *Petasites* spp.

Additional material. Zhytomyr: Zviahel, 12.07.1978, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK). Crimea: no exact data (VUS).

3. *Acinia biflexa* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Luhansk; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Korneyev et al. (2016); Korneyev & Konovalov (2010); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. On meadows with *Inula britannica*.

4. *Acinia corniculata* (Zetterstedt, 1819)

Distribution in Ukraine: Zhytomyr*; Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

Remarks. On meadows with *Centaurea jacea*.

Additional material. Zhytomyr: Zviahel, 24.08.1978, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

5. *Aciura coryli* (Rossi, 1794)

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Odesa.

References. Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021); iNaturalist.

Remarks. In steppes, associated with Lamiaceae.

6. *Actinoptera discoidea* (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski, 1877 b (as *Tephritis gnaphalii*); V. Korneyev (1985 b).

Remarks. In flower heads of *Helichrysum arenarium*.

7. *Anomoia purmunda* (Harris, 1780)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Luhansk.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Korneyev & Konovalov (2010); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Apparently everywhere in association with *Crataegus*, *Cotoneaster*, *Pyracantha*, *Sorbus* and related Rosaceae plants.

8. *Campiglossa absinthii* (Fabricius, 1805)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. In ruderal vegetation, infesting flower heads of *Artemisia absinthium*, apparently in most regions of Ukraine.

9. *Campiglossa achyrophori* (Loew, 1869)

Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.

References. S. Korneyev (2011).

10. *Campiglossa argyrocephala* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy.

References. Zrazhevsky & Korneyev (1989).

Remarks. On wet meadows with *Achillea ptarmica* and related plant species.

11. *Campiglossa bidentis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Mykolaiv; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 b) (as *Tephritis elongatula*); Bukowsky (1940) (as *Paroxyna absinthii*); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); S. Korneyev (2011); Korneyev et al. (2016) (as *Dioxyyna*), Korneyev et al. (2021 a); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. In meadows and ruderal vegetation with *Bidens* spp., apparently in most regions of Ukraine.

◦ ***Campiglossa difficilis* (Hendel, 1927)**

References. Dirlbek & Dirlbek (1964: Crimea).

Remarks. Not found. Dirlbeks' material is a misidentified *C. producta*. May occur in the Carpathians; in association with *Taraxacum serotinum*.

12. *Campiglossa daronici* (Loew, 1856)

Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.

References. S. Korneyev (2011).

13. *Campiglossa grandinata* (Rondani, 1870)

Distribution in Ukraine: no records.

Remarks. Not found. Possibly in the Carpathians. Occurs in Central Europe in association with *Solidago virgaurea*.

◦ ***Campiglossa guttella* (Rondani, 1870)**

Distribution in Ukraine: possibly Transcarpathia.

References. S. Korneyev (2011).

Remarks. Additional material including females is necessary to confirm its presence.

14. *Campiglossa irrorata* (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b).

Remarks. Associated with *Artemisia campestris*.

15. *Campiglossa loewiana* (Hendel, 1927)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Transcarpathia.

References. V. Korneyev (1983, 1985 b); S. Korneyev (2011).

Remarks. Associated with *Solidago virgaurea*.

16. *Campiglossa misella* (Loew, 1869)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Luhansk.

References. Nowicky (1869) (as *Tephritis lusoria*); V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & Konovalov (2010); Korneyev et al. (2016); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Associated with *Artemisia vulgaris*.

17. *Campiglossa plantaginis* (Haliday, 1833)

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Kherson*.

References. Korneyev & Konovalov (2010); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. On salt marshes and meadows, associated with *Tripolium pannonicum*.

Additional material. Kherson: Black Sea Biosphere Reserve, Yagorlytskyi gulf, 6–8.08.1985, ex flower heads of “*Aster tripolium*”, 2♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

18. *Campiglossa producta* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b) (as *Paroxyna tessellata*); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

◦ ***Campiglossa punctella* (Fallén, 1814)**

Remarks. Not reliable records. Associated with *Artemisia campestris* and *A. absinthii* (Merz, 1994).

◦ ***Campiglossa solidaginis* (White, 1986)**

Remarks. No records. Associated with *Solidago virgaurea* (White, 1986).

19. *Carpomya (Carpomya) schineri* (Loew, 1856)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Luhansk.

References. V. Korneyev (1983, 1985 b); Korneyev & Konovalov (2010); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).

Remarks. Apparently everywhere in association with wild and planted roses.

20. *Carpomya (Carpomya) vesuviana* (Costa, 1854)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson; Crimea.

References. Trikoz & Litvnova (2007); Korneyev et al. (2018).

Remarks. In fruits of planted *Zyzyphus jujuba*.

21. *Carpomya (Goniglossum) wiedemanni* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy; Poltava (?); Kharkiv (?); Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 a); Richter (1960); Korneyev et al. (2018); Ilminska & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Records by Jaroszewski (1877 a) from Poltava and Kharkiv may belong to a similar, but more common *C. (C.) schineri* and need confirmation, but no voucher specimens have been found either in Kharkiv or in St. Petersburg collections, which house most specimens collected by Jaroszewski.

22. *Carpomya (Myiopardalis) pardalina* (Bigot, 1891)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson.

References. Korneyev et al. (2018).

Remarks. Pest of melons (*Cucumis melo*).

23. *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann, 1824)

Distribution in Ukraine: Odesa; regularly intercepted as a quarantine species; possibly established in southern regions (Klechkovsky, pers. comm.).

24. *Chaetorellia acrolophi* White & Marcquart, 1989**Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Ternopil; Luhansk.**References.** Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as “*Chaetorellia* sp. aff. *jaceae*”); Korneyev et al. (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Centaurea stoebe* and *Cent. diffusa*.**25. *Chaetorellia australis* Hering, 1940****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Cherkasy; Ternopil.**References.** Korneyev (2003); Korneyev et al. (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Centaurea cyanus*.**26. *Chaetorellia jaceae* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Crimea.**References.** V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Widespread, possibly everywhere in association with *Centaurea jacea* and *Cent. phrygia* or related species.**27. *Chaetorellia loricata* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Crimea.**References.** Korneyev (1985); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Associated with *Centaurea scabiosa*.**28. *Chaetostomella cylindrica* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.**References.** Jaroszewski (1878) (as *Trypeta onotrophes*); Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as *C. onotrophes*); Korneyev et al. (2016).**Remarks.** A poorly understood aggregation of host races associated with certain *Carduus*, *Cirsium*, *Centaurea* and *Serratula* species and possibly other Asteraceae Cardueae plants.**29. *Chaetostomella rossica* Hendel, 1927****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Chernihiv; Luhansk; Kherson.**References.** Korneyev (1985 a, 1987 c); Korneyev et al. (2021 a); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).**Remarks.** Associated with psammophilous species of *Jurinea*.**Additional material:** Poznyaky Cemetary, 2.08.1989, 3♂, 2♀ (V. Korneyev leg.) (SIZK).**◦ *Chetostoma stackelbergi* (Rohdendorf, 1955)****Remarks.** Not found. Associated with *Lonicera* in western and northern Europe.**30. *Dithryca guttularis* (Meigen, 1826)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi.**References.** Mihalyi (1959); V. Korneyev (1985; 2002); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Associated with *Achillea*.**31. *Ensina sonchi* (Linnaeus, 1767)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson.**References.** Jaroszewski (1878); Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Larvae in many genera of Asteraceae Cichorieae.**32. *Euaresta bullans* (Wiedemann, 1830)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Ternopil; Kherson; Crimea.**References.** Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Xanthium spinosum* in ruderal vegetation.**33. *Euleia heraclei* (Linnaeus, 1758)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Luhansk.**References.** V. Korneyev (1991 b); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Larvae mine leaves of various Apiaceae.**34. *Euleia rotundiventris* (Fallén, 1814)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv.**References.** V. Korneyev (1987 c; 1991 a).**Remarks.** Larvae mine leaves of various Apiaceae.**35. *Euphranta (Euphranta) connexa* (Fabricius, 1794)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Luhansk.**References.** Jaroszewski, 1882 (Birky); Korneyev (1983, 1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).**36. *Euphranta (Rhacochlaena) toxoneura* (Loew, 1846)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Ternopil.**References.** Korneyev (1982; 1985 b); Korneyev et al. (2016).**Remarks.** Larvae in galls of *Potania* sawflies on *Salix*.**37. *Eurasimona stigma* (Loew, 1840)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Cherkasy; Kharkiv.**References.** Jaroszewski, 1877 b; Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as *Urophora stigma*); Korneyev & White (1991) (as *Urophora (Eurasimona) stigma*).**38. *Hemilea dimidiata* (Costa, 1844)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Transcarpathia.**References.** Korneyev & Korneyev (2015).**Remarks.** Larvae mines leaves of *Taraxacum* (Merz, 1994).

- 39. *Heringina guttata* (Fallén, 1814)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Sumy; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Luhansk; Mykolaiv.
References. Jaroszewski (1877 a); Korneyev (2016).
Remarks. Associated with *Helichrysum arenarium*.
- 40. *Hypenidium graecum* (Loew, 1862)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea.
References. Richter (1960) (as *H. novaki*); V. Korneyev et al. (2011).
- 41. *Ictericodes japonicus* (Wiedemann, 1830)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Luhansk; Crimea.
References. Jaroszewski (1877 a) (as *Oxyphora schneideri*); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. On wet meadows. Associated with *Penthanema britannicum*.
- 42. *Inuromaesa maura* (Frauenfeld, 1857)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Crimea.
References. Korneyev & White (1991) (as *Urophora (Inuromaesa) maura*).
Remarks. On meadows. Associated with *Penthanema ensifolium* and *P. salicinum*.
- 43. *Merzomyia westermanni* (Meigen, 1826)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk.
References. Korneyev & Konovalov (2010).
Remarks. Associated with *Jacobaea erucifolia* and *J. vulgaris* (Merz, 1994) (as *Senecio erucifolous* and *S. jacobaea*).
- 44. *Myoleja lucida* (Fallén, 1826)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.
References. S. Korneyev (2011).
Remarks. Associated with *Lonicera* spp.
- 45. *Myopites blotii* Brebisson, 1827**
Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea.
References. V. Korneyev (2003) (as *M. apicatus*).
Remarks. On meadows. Associated with *Pulicaria dysenterica*.
- 46. *Myopites inulae* (Roder, 1840)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Crimea.
References. Korneyev et al. (2016) (as *M. inulaedyssentericae*); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).
Remarks. On meadows. Associated with *Pentanema ensifolia* and *P. salicina*.
- ***Myopites tenellus* (Frauenfeld, 1863)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records
Remarks. On meadows. Associated with *Pentanema britannica*. This species occurs in Austria, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, European and Far East Russia, Kyrgyzstan, but not found in Ukraine yet, although very probably is present in some regions.
- 47. *Noeta bisetosa* Merz, 1992**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.
References. V. Korneyev (2003).
Remarks. Associated with *Hieracium piloselloides* (Merz, 1994) and possibly some other species.
- ***Noeta crepidis* Hering, 1936**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
Remarks. Associated with *Crepis biennis* (Merz, 1994). The species was known only from its type locality in Germany (Magdeburg), but no reliable recently collected material or records are known. Merz (1994) recorded it from Lower Austria and Hungary. Can be found in Ukraine.
- 48. *Noeta pupillata* (Fallén, 1814)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Luhansk.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b).
Remarks. Associated with *Hieracium murorum*, *H. umbellatum* (Merz, 1994) and possibly some other species.
- 49. *Oedaspis multifasciata* (Loew, 1850)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson.
References. V. Korneyev (1987 c; 2002).
Remarks. Larvae induce subterranean bud galls on rhizome of *Artemisia campestris* (incl. *A. marshalliana*) (Korneyev, 1987 c; Merz, 1994).
- 50. *Orellia falcata* (Scopoli, 1763)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.
References. Jaroszewski (1878); V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).
Remarks. Associated with *Tragopogon dubius*, *T. orientalis* — larvae in stems (Korneyev, 1985 b, Merz, 1994).
- 51. *Orellia scorzonerae* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson.
References. V. Korneyev (1987 c) (as *Orellia distans*).
Remarks. Associated with *Scorzonera humilis* and *S. parviflora* (V. Korneyev, 1987 c; Merz, 1994).
- 52. *Orellia stictica* (Gmelin, 1790)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Cherkasy; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.
References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev (1987 c) (as *O. punctata*); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. Associated with *Tragopogon borysthenticus*, *T. orientalis*, *Scorzonera parviflora* and *Taraxacum serotinum* (Korneyev, 1987 c; Merz, 1994).
- ***Oxyaciura tibialis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
Remarks. Associated with *Lavandula* and other Lamiaceae.
- 53. *Oxyna albipila* (Loew, 1869)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Kherson.

- References.** V. Korneyev (1985 b, 1987 c).
Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Artemisia campestris* (incl. *A. marshalliana*) (Korneyev, 1987 c).
- 54. *Oxya flavipennis* (Loew, 1844)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Luhansk; Crimea.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. Larvae in rhizome galls on *Achillea*.
- 55. *Oxya nebulosa* (Wiedemann, 1817)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Luhansk.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. Larvae in rhizome galls on *Leucanthemum vulgare*. *Oxya nasuta* Hering, 1936 described from Ukraine is a synonym.
- 56. *Oxya parietina* (Linnaeus, 1758)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Luhansk; Kherson.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b).
Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Artemisia vulgaris* (V. Korneyev, 1985 b; Merz, 1994).
- 57. *Paracanthella pavonina* (Portschinsky, 1875)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea*.
References. V. Korneyev (1987 c); Korneyev & Konovalov (2010).
Remarks. Associated with *Lactuca tatarica*.
Additional material. Crimea: Donuzlav near Evpatoria, 15.08.1991, ex flower heads of *Lactuca tatarica*, exit 02.1992, 3♂, 4♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).
 ◦ ***Paracarphotricha alpestris* (Pokorný, 1887)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
Remarks. Associated with *Aster* or *Erigeron* in alpine meadows above 1800 m.
- 58. *Philophylla caesio* (Harris, 1780)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Zhytomyr*; Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Luhansk; Crimea*.
References. Jaroszewski (1886) (as *Acidia lichnidis* & *A. lychnidis*); S. Korneyev (2011); Korneyev et al. (2016); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).
Remarks. Associated with *Urtica dioica*.
Additional material. Zhytomyr: Zviahel, 24.07.1978, 1♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK); Crimea: no exact data (VUS).
 ◦ ***Platyparea carpathica* Klasa, 2001**
Distribution in Ukraine: No records.
Remarks. Occurs in the Carpathians (Poland, Bieszczady); can be found on the neighbouring territories of Ukraine.
- 59. *Platyparea discoidea* (Fabricius, 1787)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Kharkiv.
- References.** Jaroszewski (1880); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. No recent records.
- 60. *Plioreocepta poeciloptera* (Schrank, 1776)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b; 1987 a).
Remarks. In stems of *Asparagus officinalis*.
- 61. *Rhagoletis alternata* (Fallén, 1814)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b).
Remarks. Associated with planted and wild roses (*Rosa* spp.), apparently throughout the whole northern part of the country.
- 62. *Rhagoletis batava* (Hering, 1938)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Lviv.
References. Moskalets et al. (2021); Babytsky et al. (2023).
Remarks. Associated with planted sea buckthorns (*Hippophae rhamnoides*), needing further study.
- 63. *Rhagoletis berberidis* (Jermy, 1961)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.
References. V. Korneyev (1997).
- 64. *Rhagoletis cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Rivne*; Kyiv; Transcarpathia*; Khmelntsk; Mykolaiv; Kherson*; Donetsk.
References. Korneyev & Kameneva (2006); Korneyev et al. (2018).
Remarks. This species is represented by two “host races”, the “honeysuckle” and the “cherry” race; both are obviously widespread in all the parts of Ukraine where *Lonicera tatarica*, *L. xylosteum* (Caprifoliaceae), *Prunus serotina*, *P. cerasus*, *P. avium*, and *P. mahaleb* (Rosaceae) (Kandybina, 1977; Korneyev et al., 2018).
Additional material. Rivne: Rivne raion: Novostavske forestry, forest edge, 23.06.2022, 1♀ (V. Finchuk obs.); Ostroh raion, 50.327778, 26.514397 (Stanislava Ro obs.); Transcarpathia: Berehove, 13.05.2020, 29.06.2020, 4.06.2023, 1♀ (V. Hleba obs.); Kherson: Zelenivka, 46.707740, 32.610931, 14.06.2019, 1♂ (R. Mishustin obs.); Donetsk: Nikolske raion, Zoria, 47.295109, 37.620126 (V. Finchuk obs.); Shakhtarsk raion 48.064626, 38.814139, 21.07.2020, on *Lonicera tatarica* L. (A. Gubin obs.) (UkrBIN, 2024 a); Crimea: no exact data (VUS).
 ◦ ***Rhagoletis cingulata* (Loew, 1862)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
References. Korneyev et al. (2018); Babysky et al. (2023).
Remarks. Quarantine pest of cherries: *Prunus serotina*, *P. pennsylvanica*, *P. virginiana*, *P. cerasus*, *P. avium*, *P. mahaleb* (Rosaceae); invasive adventive pest in Europe.

- ***Rhagoletis completa* (Cresson, 1929)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
References. Korneyev et al. (2018); Babysky et al. (2023).
Remarks. Quarantine pest of walnuts (*Juglans*); invasive adventive pest in Europe.
- 65. *Rhagoletis flavicincta* (Enderlein, 1934)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Mykolaiv; Luhansk.
References. Rohdendorf (1961); Korneyev et al. (2018).
Remarks. In fruits of *Lonicera tatarica*, *L. korolkowii*, *L. stanantha*, *L. nummularifolia* (Caprifoliaceae) (Kandybina, 1977; Korneyev et al., 2018).
Additional material. Mykolaiv: Mighia, 21.06.2009, 48.00 N, 30.97 E, 5♂, 3♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); 22.06.2009, 3♂, 2♀ (S. Korneyev leg.); 3♂, 2♀ (S. Korneyev leg.) (SIZK).
- 66. *Rhagoletis meigenii* (Loew, 1844)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b).
Remarks. Associated with *Berberis vulgaris* (Kandybina, 1977) and *Mahonia aquifolium* (Korneyev, unpublished data).
- 67. *Sphenella marginata* (Fallén, 1814)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Zhytomyr*; Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Luhansk; Crimea*.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. Associated with numerous *Jacobaea* spp.
Additional material. Zhytomyr: Zviahel, 1.08.1978, ex flower heads of *Jacobaea vulgaris*, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK). Crimea: no exact data (VUS).
- ***Stemonocera cornuta* (Scopoli, 1763)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
Remarks. Possibly in the Carpathians.
- ***Stemonocera spinulosa* (Hering, 1936)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
Remarks. Possibly in the Carpathians.
- 68. *Stemonocera spinifrons* (Schroeder, 1913)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.
References. Korneyev & Kolcsar (2015); Korneyev & Korneyev (2015).
Remarks. Leaf miners in *Senecio fuchsii* und *Eupatorium cannabinum* (Merz, 1994).
- ***Stemonocera superciliata* (Frey, 1935)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
Remarks. Possibly in the Carpathians.
- 69. *Tephritis angustipennis* (Loew, 1844)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Mykolaiv; Kherson.
References. S. Korneyev (2016).
Remarks. On wet meadows with *Achillea ptarmica* and related species.
- 70. *Tephritis arnicae* (Linnaeus, 1758)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.
References. S. Korneyev (2011).
Remarks. In flower heads and stems of *Arnica* and *Doronicum* (Merz, 1994; Korneyev & Korneyev, 2011).
- 71. *Tephritis bardanae* (Schrank, 1803)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Zhytomyr; Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Donetsk; Luhansk; Crimea.
References. Jaroszewski (1877 a); V. Korneyev (1985 b); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).
Remarks. Widespread in ruderal vegetation, associated with *Arctium tomentosum* and *A. lappae*.
- 72. *Tephritis brachyura* Loew, 1869**
Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea.
References. Korneyev & Klasa (2016).
- 73. *Tephritis cometa* (Loew, 1840)**
Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Luhansk; Kherson.
References. Jaroszewski (1880) (Sloviansk); V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).
Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium arvense* and *Cirs. vulgare* (Kameneva, Korneyev, 1987; Merz, 1994).
- ***Tephritis conura* (Loew, 1844)**
Distribution in Ukraine: no records.
References. V. Korneyev (1985 b) (misidentification of *T. ruralis*).
Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium helenioides* in Sweden (Janzon, 1985); *Cirs. acaule*, *Cirs. erisithales*, *Cirs. heterophyllum*, *Cirs. oleraceum* and *Cirs. spinosissimum*; in England also on *Cirs. palustre* (Merz, 1994); in Kyrgyzstan, on *Cirs. albertii*, and *Cirs. polyacanthum* (Korneyev & Kameneva, 1993). Very probably, in the Capathians, assoiated with *Cirs. oleraceum*.
- 74. *Tephritis conyzifoliae* Merz, 1992**
Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.
References. S. Korneyev (2016); Korneyev & Klasa (2016).
Remarks. Associated with *Crepis conyzifolia* in Switzerland (Merz, 1994) and *Cr. pannonica* and *Cr. sibirica* in Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).
- 75. *Tephritis crepidis* Hendel, 1927**
Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Ivano-Frankivsk; Chernivtsi.
References. Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021); Korneyev & Klasa (2016).
Remarks. Associated with *Crepis biennis* and *C. pyrenaica* in Switzerland (Merz, 1994).

76. *Tephritis dilacerata* (Loew, 1846)**Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Cherkasy; Luhansk.**References.** S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Sonchus arvensis* in Switzerland (Merz, 1994) and *S. palustris* in Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016).**77. *Tephritis dioscurea* (Loew, 1856)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Sumy; Ternopil; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Crimea.**References.** V. Korneyev (1985 b); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Associated with *Achillea millefolium*.**78. *Tephritis divisa* Rondani, 1871****Distribution in Ukraine:** Khmelnytsky; Vinnytsia; Crimea.**References.** V. Korneyev (2003); S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Picris echioides* (Merz, 1994).**79. *Tephritis dudichi* Aczel, 1939****Distribution in Ukraine:** Transcarpathia.**References.** Korneyev & Korneyev (2011).**Remarks.** Associated with *Telekia speciosa*, *Inula grandiflora* (S. Korneyev, 2016), and *I. hirta* (Merz, 1994).**80. *Tephritis fallax* (Loew, 1844)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Ivano-Frankivsk.**References.** S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Leontodon hispidus* (Merz, 1994).**81. *Tephritis formosa* (Loew, 1844)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Crimea.**References.** Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).**Remarks.** Associated with *Sonchus asper*, *S. oleraceus*, *S. arvensis* (Merz, 1994).**82. *Tephritis heliophila* Hendel, 1927****Distribution in Ukraine:** Ivano-Frankivsk.**References.** S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Larvae in stem galls on *Tragopogon dubius* (Merz, 1994).**83. *Tephritis hendeliana* Hering, 1944****Distribution in Ukraine:** Ternopil; Crimea*.**References.** S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Carduus nutans* (Merz, 1994) and *Card. thoermeri* (Korneyev & Kameneva, 1992).**Additional material.** Crimea: no exact data (VUS).**84. *Tephritis hurvitzi* Freidberg, 1981****Distribution in Ukraine:** Chernivtsi; Kyrovohrad; Zaporizhzhya; Crimea.**References.** V. Korneyev (2003); S. Korneyev (2016); Korneyev et al. (2021 b).**Remarks.** Larvae in flowerhead galls on *Tragopogon longirostris* and *Scorzonera syriaca* (Freidberg & Küttik, 2004) and apparently some other species assigned to these genera.**85. *Tephritis hyoscyami* (Linnaeus, 1758)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Chernihiv; Sumy; Ternopil; Khmelnytsky; Vinnytsia; Kharkiv; Donetsk; Luhansk; Odesa; Crimea.**References.** Jaroszewski (1880) (Sloviansk); S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Carduus crispus*, *Card. defloratus*, and *Card. personata* (Merz, 1994).**86. *Tephritis leontodontis* (DeGeer, 1776)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Cherkasy; Kharkiv.**References.** Jaroszewski (1877 a); Kryshchal (1949); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & Klasa (2016)**Remarks.** Associated with *Leontodon autumnalis*, *L. helveticus*, *L. hispidus* (Merz, 1994).**87. *Tephritis matricariae* (Loew, 1844)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Hering (1937): Ternopil ("Krywczce). Not represented in our material. Possibly, a misidentification of *T. crepidis* (Korneyev et al. (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Crepis taraxacifolia*, *C. foetida*, *C. vesicaria* (Merz, 1994).**88. *Tephritis mutabilis* Merz, 1992****Distribution in Ukraine:** Transcarpathia.**References.** Korneyev & Klasa (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Leontodon hispidus* (Merz, 1994).**89. *Tephritis neesii* (Meigen, 1830)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Kyiv; Chernivtsi.**References.** Jaroszewski (1877 b) (as *Tephritis conjuncta*); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).**Remarks.** Associated with *Leucanthemum vulgare* (Merz, 1994).**90. *Tephritis oedipus* Hendel, 1927****Distribution in Ukraine:** Luhansk; Kherson; Zaporizhzhya; Donetsk.**References.** Korneyev & Karpiuk (2009); S. Korneyev (2016).**Remarks.** Associated with *Lactuca tatarica* (Korneyev & Kameneva, 1993).**91. *Tephritis postica* (Loew, 1844)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Odesa; Crimea.**References.** Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); S. Korneyev (2016); Korneyev & Korneyev (2018); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).**Remarks.** Associated with *Onopordum acanthium*.**92. *Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844)****Distribution in Ukraine:** Ternopil; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1987 c); S. Korneyev (2016); Korneyev et al. (2023).

Remarks. Associated with *Calendula arvensis*, *Cal. officinalis* (including cultivated).

92. *Tephritis pulchra* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia; Crimea.

References. S. Korneyev (2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Scorzonera jaquiniana*, *S. humilis*, *S.* (= *Podospermum*) *laciniata* (Merz, 1994; S. Korneyev, 2016).

93. *Tephritis ruralis* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Sumy; Ternopil; Khmelnytsky; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Ivano-Frankivsk; Odesa.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Hieracium pilosella*, *H. lactuella* (Merz, 1994)

94. *Tephritis separata* (Rondani, 1871)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Kharkiv; Chernivtsi; Donetsk; Luhansk; Mykolaiv; Crimea.

References. Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Picris hieracioides* (Hering, 1937) and *P. rigida* (Korneyev et al., 2016).

95. *Tephritis tanacetii* Hering, 1956

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.

References. Korneyev & Klasa (2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Tanacetum corymbosum* (Merz, 1994) and *T. vulgare* (S. Korneyev, 2016).

96. *Tephritis truncata* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); S. Korneyev (2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Leontodon tenuiflorus*, *L. incanus*, and *L. crispus* in Austria and Italy (Merz, 1994).

97. *Tephritis valida* (Loew, 1858)

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Chernivtsi.

References. Korneyev et al. (2016; 2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Inula helenium*.

98. *Tephritis vespertina* (Loew, 1844)

Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.

References. S. Korneyev (2011, 2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Hypochoeris radicata* (Merz, 1994).

◦ ***Tephritis zernyi* (Hendel, 1927)**

Distribution in Ukraine: no records.

Remarks. In western Europe, the populations associated with *Arctium minus* (possibly occurring in Ukraine) are considered either to be a separate species, *T. zernyi* (e.g., Merz, 1994), or a host race (Diegisser et

al., 2004). Additional studies, including in Ukraine, are needed.

99. *Terellia (Cerajocera) ceratocera* (Hendel, 1913)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

Remarks. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa*.

100. *Terellia (Cerajocera) clarissima* Korneyev, 1987

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Kherson.

References. V. Korneyev (1987 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Jurinea laxa* (and possibly other psammphilous species of the genus).

101. *Terellia (Cerajocera) cyanoides* Korneyev, 2003

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv*; Chernihiv.

References. V. Korneyev (2003).

Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Jurinea cyanodes* (and possibly other psammphilous species of the genus).

Additional material. Kyiv: Vovchi Buhry nr Soshnykiv, sands, 50.03, 31.14, 10.06.2010, swept from *Jurinea* sp., 1♂, 2♀ (S. & V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

102. *Terellia (Cerajocera) gynaeochroma* (Hering, 1937)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Khmelnytsky; Cherkasy; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1878) (*Trypeta lappae*); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as *Terellia (Cerajocera) lappae*); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Onopordum acanthium*.

103. *Terellia (Cerajocera) nigrinota* (Korneyev, 1985)

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987).

Remarks. Associated with *Arctium* spp.

104. *Terellia (Cerajocera) plagiata* (Dahlbom, 1850)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Luhansk.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Centaurea scabiosa*.

105. *Terellia (Cerajocera) setifera* (Hendel, 1927)

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Vinnytsia*; Mykolaiv; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1989); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. Larvae in stems of *Jurinea mollis* and possibly other calciphilous species.

Additional material. Vinnytsia: Busha, 48.34, 28.13, 20.06.2020, ex stems of *Jurinea* sp., 1♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

106. *Terellia (Cerajocera) tussilaginis* (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Poltava; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Arctium* spp.

107. *Terellia (Terellia) colon* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa*.

108. *Terellia (Terellia) longicauda* (Meigen, 1838)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernivtsi.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).

Remarks. Larvae in flower heads of *Cirsium eriophorum* (Merz, 1994) and *Cirs. decussatum* (= *C. polonicum*) (Korneyev et al., 2021 a).

◦ ***Terellia (Terellia) luteola* (Wiedemann, 1830)**

Distribution in Ukraine: no records.

Remarks. Associated with *Carthamus lanatus* and *Cart.* spp., which is restricted mostly to southern Crimea in Ukraine, with a few records of plant in Odesa and Mykolaiv, but this fly species is not represented in collections.

109. *Terellia (Terellia) odontolophi* Korneyev, 1993

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Odesa.

References. V. Korneyev (1993); Vasil'kovskaya & Korneyev (2005).

Remarks. In Ukraine, associated with *Psephellus trinervius* (= *Centaurea trinervia*, *Odontholophus trinervius*) (V. Korneyev, 1993), in Volga basin also with *P. sumensis* (= *Cent. sumensis*); in Armenia, with *P. phaeopappoides* (= *Cent. phaeopappoides*) (Evstigneev & Glukhova, 2021).

110. *Terellia (Terellia) orheana* Korneyev, 1990

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Odesa.

References. Vasil'kovskaya & Korneyev (2005); V. Korneyev (2006); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Associated with *Jurinea stoechadifolia* and *J. multiflora*. Apparently more widespread in southern Ukraine.

111. *Terellia (Terellia) pseudovirens* (Hering, 1940)

Distribution in Ukraine: Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Odesa; Kherson.

References. V. Korneyev (1982); Vasil'kovskaya & Korneyev (2005); Korneyev et al. (2021 a); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Associated with *Serratula xeranthemoides*, *S. radiata* and *S.* spp. (including species assigned to *Klasea*).

112. *Terellia (Terellia) ruficauda* (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Luhansk.

References. Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. *Terellia ruficauda* is believed to be an aggregation of two or more "host races" associated in Europe and Ukraine with *Cirsium arvense* and *Cirs. oleraceum* (as well as other species); their actual status needs further studies.

113. *Terellia (Terellia) serratulae* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1878) (on *Cirsium serrulatum*); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. *Terellia serratulae* is believed to be an aggregation of "host races" associated with various *Carduus* and *Cirsium* species as well as other genera; their actual status needs further studies.

114. *Terellia (Terellia) virens* (Loew, 1846)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Kharkiv; Luhansk; Odesa; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea stoebe* (= *Cent. biebersteini*, *Cent. maculosa*, *Cent. pseudomaculoisa*, etc.) and *Cent. diffusa*.

115. *Terellia (Terellia) winthemi* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Luhansk.

References. Jaroszewski (1880) (Sloviansk); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium acanthoides*.

116. *Trupanea amoena* (Frauenfeld, 1857)

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy; Mykolaiv*; Kherson; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b).

Remarks. Associated with *Lactuca serriola*, *L. sativa* and possibly other plants.

Additional material. Mykolayiv: Myhiya, 48.01, 30.98, 21.07.2009, on *Lactuca serriola*, 1♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

117. *Trupanea stellata* (Fuesslin, 1775)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Poltava; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Kyrovohrad; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 b); Kryshtal, 1949; Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Wide oligophagous species associated with various composite plants, first of all, *Crepis*, *Leontodon*, *Senecio*, *Hieracium*, *Centaurea*, *Acroptilon* and many other plants.

118. *Trypeta artemisiae* (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv.

References. Korneyev & Korneyev (2015).

Remarks. Leaf miner in *Artemisia vulgaris*; also in *Achillea ptarmica*, *Artemisia absinthium*, *Leucanthemum vulgare*, *Tanacetum vulgare*, *Eupatorium cannabinum*, *Senecio vulgaris* (Merz, 1994).

119. *Trypeta immaculata* (Macquart, 1835)

Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.

References. Korneyev & Korneyev (2015).

Remarks. Leaf miner in *Hieracium* spp., *Hypochoeris* spp., *Lapsana communis*, *Leontodon* spp., *Mycelis muralis*, *Taraxacum* spp. (Merz, 1994), in humid areas.

120. *Trypeta zoe* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil.

References. Korneyev & Korneyev (2015); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. Leaf miner in *Solidago virgaurea*, *Jacobaea* spp., *Tussilago farfara*, and also *Adenostyles glabra*, *Artemisia vulgaris*, *A. absinthium*, *Leucanthemum vulgare*, *Eupatorium cannabinum*, *Petasites albus* (Merz, 1994).

121. *Urophora affinis* Frauenfeld, 1857

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1996); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea stoebe* and *Cent. diffusa*.

122. *Urophora aprica* (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy.

References. Korneyev & White (1993).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea cyanus*.

123. *Urophora cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Luhansk.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1996).

Remarks. In twig galls on *Cirsium arvense*. Widespread along rivers and lakes on wet meadows.

124. *Urophora congrua* (Loew, 1862)

Distribution in Ukraine: Transcarpathia.

References. Mihalyi (1959); S. Korneyev (2011).

Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium erisithales*.

125. *Urophora cuspidata* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1996); Korneyev et al. (2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea scabiosa*, and *Cent. salonitana*.

126. *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld, 1867

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil; Chernivtsi.

References. Korneyev & White (1992); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Echinops exhaltatus*.

127. *Urophora jaceana* (Hering, 1935)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1996); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea jacea*.

128. *Urophora kasachstanica* (Richter, 1964)

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Kherson.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1993).

Remarks. Associated with *Acroptilon repens*.

129. *Urophora korneyevi* White, 1999

Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as *Urophora* sp.); Korneyev & White (1993) (as *Urophora arctii*).

Remarks. Associated with *Arctium major*. Possibly a synonym of *U. terebrans*.

130. *Urophora lopholomae* Korneyev & White, 1989

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as “*U. aprica* auctt. nec Loew”); Korneyev & White (1996); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea scabiosa*.

131. *Urophora mauritanica* Macquart, 1851

Distribution in Ukraine: Odesa; Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987) (as *U. macrura*); Korneyev & White (1996).

Remarks. Associated with *Carthamus lanatus*.

Additional material: Odesa region, Tarutynskyi steppe, 46.25 N, 29.42 E, 16.06.2011, 2♂ (Pljushch leg.) (SIZK).

◦ ***Urophora pauperata* (Zaitzev, 1945)**

Distribution in Ukraine: no records.

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea calcitrapa* and *Cent. iberica*. Possibly in Crimea.

132. *Urophora quadrifasciata* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Odesa; Kherson; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1992); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021 a).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea stoebe*, *Cent. diffusa*, *Cent. jacea* and some other species.

133. *Urophora sirunaseva* (Hering, 1940)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kherson; Crimea.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1993).

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea solstitialis*.

134. *Urophora solstitialis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Luhansk; Kherson; Crimea.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1993); Korneyev et al. (2016).

Remarks. Associated with *Carduus* spp.

135. *Urophora stylata* (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Chernivtsi; Luhansk; Kherson.

References. V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); V. Korneyev (1987 c); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium arvense* and *Cirs. vulgare*.

136. *Urophora terebrans* (Loew, 1850)

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Mykolaiv; Kherson.

References. Korneyev & White (1993).

Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium serrulatum* (= *Cirs. ukrainicum*), *Cirs. eriophorum* and *Onopordum acanthium*, possibly with two generations on different plants.

137. *Urophora trinervii* Korneyev & White, 1996

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk.

References. Korneyev & White (1996).

Remarks. Associated with *Psephellus trinervius* (= *Centaurea trinervia*).

138. *Urophora variabilis* (Loew, 1869)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kharkiv; Luhansk; Mykolaiv; Kherson.

References. Jaroszewski (1878) (as *Urophora congrua* on *Cirsium serrulatum*); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); V. Korneyev (1987 c); Korneyev & White (1993).

Remarks. Associated with *Cirsium serrulatum* (= *Cirs. ukrainicum*),

139. *Urophora vera* V. Korneyev & White, 1996

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk*.

References. Korneyev & White (1996); Kameneva & Korneyev (2024).

Remarks. Associated with *Serratula* cf. *radiata*.

140. *Urophora xanthippe* (Munro, 1934)

Distribution in Ukraine: Luhansk; Kherson.

References. Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev & White (1993).

Remarks. Associated with *Acroptilon repens*.

◦ *Xyphosia laticauda* (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution in Ukraine: no records.

Remarks. Associated with *Centaurea montana*. Possibly in the Carpathians.

141. *Xyphosia miliaria* (Schrank, 1781)

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv; Chernihiv; Ternopil; Cherkasy; Poltava; Kharkiv; Transcarpathia; Chernivtsi; Kyrovohrad; Luhansk; Mykolaiv; Kherson; Crimea.

References. Jaroszewski (1877 b); V. Korneyev (1985 b); Kameneva & Korneyev (1987); Korneyev et al. (2016, 2021).

Remarks. Associated with various *Cirsium* spp. and *Carduus* spp.

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